

Living Between Sexes: A Phenomenological Inquiry on Intersex Self-Image

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of Filipino intersex individuals in relation to the formation, negotiation, and acceptance of their self-image. Intersex individuals are born with biological sex characteristics that do not conform to conventional binary definitions of male and female, often resulting in psychological, social, and legal challenges. Despite increasing global discourse on intersex rights and healthcare, limited research has examined the self-image of intersex individuals within the Philippine cultural context. Grounded in Rosenberg's theory of self-image and supported by frameworks such as self-discrepancy theory, PERMA, and Kübler-Ross's stages of grief, the study sought to understand how intersex individuals perceive and ultimately accept themselves.

Using a qualitative phenomenological design, the researchers conducted an online focus group discussion with ten Filipino intersex individuals affiliated with Intersex Philippines. Data were analyzed using Colaizzi's seven-step descriptive phenomenological method. Findings revealed nine emergent themes, including appearance and aesthetics, biological realities, encountered mismatching, autonomy in self-image formation, the journey to acceptance, and the role of intersex forums in fostering belongingness and resilience. Participants described experiences of discrimination, emotional struggle, identity incongruence, and social invisibility; however, they also demonstrated resilience, autonomy, and self-acceptance. Peer support and community belonging emerged as significant factors in the acceptance process.

The study concludes that intersex self-image acceptance is a deeply personal, non-linear, and ongoing process shaped by biological realities, social experiences, autonomy, and community support. The findings contribute to intersex advocacy, psychological practice, and inclusive policy development in the Philippines.

INTRODUCTION

The question of who we are—biologically, psychologically, and socially—sits at the heart of human identity. For most people, the alignment between their biological sex, social gender, and personal self-image is taken for granted. For intersex individuals, however, this alignment is fundamentally disrupted from birth, generating a cascade of physical, psychological, and social challenges that the wider public rarely understands. Intersex refers to individuals born with physical or biological sex characteristics—such as sex chromosomes, hormones, sexual anatomy, or reproductive organs—that do not conform to typical medical definitions of male and female (Hostman, 2020). Far from being a rare anomaly, it is estimated that intersex conditions affect approximately 1.7% of the global population—a prevalence comparable to that of red hair (Blackless et al., 2000).

Globally, intersex individuals face systematic medicalization of their bodies from infancy, often subjected to non-consensual surgical and hormonal interventions intended to normalize their anatomy to fit binary sex categories (Carpenter, 2018; Human Rights Watch, 2017). The United Nations Committee Against Torture and the World Health Organization have both called for an end to unnecessary medical interventions on intersex children, recognizing these as violations of bodily autonomy and human rights (United Nations, 2015; WHO, 2015). Despite these declarations, the majority of intersex individuals continue

to experience their conditions as sources of shame, secrecy, and medical pathologization rather than as natural biological variation (Fausto-Sterling, 2019; Roen, 2019). The psychological consequences are significant: intersex individuals report elevated rates of anxiety, depression, and difficulties with identity formation compared to the general population (Van de Grift et al., 2018).

At the national level, the Philippines presents a distinctive socio-cultural landscape for intersex experiences. The concept of intersexuality in the Philippines predates Western colonial influence, as evidenced in indigenous mythology, folklore, and pre-colonial spiritual traditions. Lakapati, also known as Ikapati of the Tagalogs, is the deity of fertility and good harvest depicted as possessing both male and female attributes—reflecting a historical fluidity in Philippine gender conceptualization that contemporary legislation has yet to fully honor (Chan, 2018; Clark, 2018). The landmark legal case of Jeff Cagandahan in 2003 marked a significant, albeit isolated, judicial acknowledgment of intersex identity in the Philippines, wherein the Supreme Court affirmed the right of an intersex individual to determine their own gender identity based on their lived experience and biological development (OutrageMag.com Staff, 2018). Nonetheless, no comprehensive legislative framework specifically protects intersex individuals in the Philippines; the SOGIE Equality Bill, which would extend protections to people of diverse sexual orientations, gender

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identities, and expressions, remains pending as of this writing (Divina Law, 2021).

At the local level, the invisibility of intersex individuals in Philippine society is striking. A CNN Philippines report by Mendoza (2019) documented the profound social isolation, harassment, and discrimination experienced by Filipino intersex individuals in everyday settings such as public restrooms, schools, and workplaces. An informal online community—the only known intersex-specific group in the country—had expanded to only 40 members at the time of the report, illustrating the extreme marginalization and stigmatization that inhibits disclosure and community formation (CNN Philippines, 2019). The SOGIE Equality Bill, as affirmed by international human rights instruments including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, seeks to protect all individuals—including intersex persons—from discrimination in both private and public institutions (Divina Law, 2021).

Despite growing international scholarship on intersex health and rights, research specifically examining the psychological self-image of intersex individuals within Filipino cultural contexts remains extremely limited. The concept of self-image, as defined by Morris Rosenberg (1965) in his foundational work *Society and the Adolescent Self-Image*, comprises three elements: how one perceives oneself, how one interprets others' perceptions of oneself, and one's ideal self. For intersex individuals, each of these dimensions is profoundly complicated by biological ambiguity, social stigma, and the coercive normalization pressures of binary gender systems.

Grounded in this convergence of global, national, and local concerns, the present study employs a phenomenological approach to document and analyze the lived experiences of Filipino intersex individuals as they navigate the construction and acceptance of their self-image. By giving voice to a population that has been historically silenced and medicalized, this research aims to contribute empirical and humanistic knowledge that can inform psychological practice, healthcare policy, and advocacy efforts in the Philippines.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The following review synthesizes existing scholarship around three overarching themes directly relevant to the lived experiences of intersex individuals: (1) the biological and medical dimensions of intersex conditions; (2) the social, legal, and cultural contexts shaping intersex identity; and (3) the psychological dimensions of self-image, identity formation, and acceptance.

Biological and Medical Dimensions of Intersex

Intersex is an umbrella term encompassing a wide range of congenital conditions in which chromosomal, gonadal, hormonal, or anatomical sex characteristics do not conform to conventional binary classifications (Witchel, 2018). The medical community has historically categorized these variations under the rubric of Disorders of Sexual Development (DSDs), a terminology that—while clinically useful—carries pathologizing connotations that many intersex advocates and affected individuals reject (Monro et al., 2021). Previously described using the derogatory terms hermaphroditism and pseudohermaphroditism, current best practice favors the term intersex as a less stigmatizing and more politically appropriate descriptor (ISNA, n.d.).

Specific intersex conditions documented in the literature include Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH), Turner Syndrome, Klinefelter Syndrome, Swyer Syndrome, complete and partial androgen insensitivity syndromes (CAIS/PAIS), and true gonadal dysgenesis, each presenting distinct patterns of

biological variation with differing implications for fertility, hormonal functioning, and physical development (Akinal, 2017; Banoth et al., 2017; Rowlands & Amy, 2018; Witchel, 2018). Rich et al. (2016) have further documented the role of endocrine-disrupting chemicals in the increasing prevalence of intersex variations, highlighting the interaction between environmental and genetic factors in sex development.

A particularly salient issue for intersex individuals is infertility, which affects many but not all intersex persons and is often diagnosed simultaneously with the intersex condition itself (Jones, 2019). For intersex individuals assigned female at birth, infertility carries additional psychosocial weight given the cultural stigmatization of women who cannot bear children (Jones, 2019). Menstrual experience is similarly variable: some intersex individuals experience menstruation, others do not, depending on which reproductive organs are present and functional (Natracare, n.d.). These biological realities—infertility, hormonal anomalies, atypical anatomical structures—form the material basis upon which intersex individuals must construct their self-image.

Social, Legal, and Cultural Contexts of Intersex Identity

The social experience of being intersex is profoundly shaped by the binary gender systems that pervade legal, medical, and cultural institutions. Holzer (2020) documents how mismatching between intersex individuals' physical characteristics and their legal gender documentation—birth certificates, identification documents—routinely exposes them to harassment, discrimination, and exclusion from housing and employment. This legal invisibility compounds the social marginalization that intersex individuals face in everyday settings, from school uniforms to public restrooms (Mendoza, 2019).

In educational and workplace contexts, intersex individuals frequently encounter stigmatization rooted in the hegemonic classification systems that position non-normative bodies as deviant (Edge, 2019). Goffman's (1959) concept of impression management illuminates the strategies intersex individuals employ to navigate social environments—including strategic clothing choices, selective disclosure, and the performance of socially assigned gender roles—as means of managing others' perceptions and minimizing stigmatization. Clothing, in particular, functions as a site of identity negotiation for intersex individuals, who often dress in ways that satisfy social or institutional requirements rather than reflecting their own gender identity (Chauhan et al., 2019; Reilly & McGuire, 2018).

Within the Philippine cultural context, the LGBTQIA+ community—including intersex individuals—exists in a complex socio-legal environment. While Philippine popular culture is relatively tolerant of gender diversity in certain respects, structural protections remain absent. The pending SOGIE Equality Bill represents the most significant legislative effort to date to protect gender and sexually diverse individuals from discrimination, and its continued failure to pass reflects the influence of conservative religious institutions on Philippine politics (Divina Law, 2021). In this context, intersex advocacy groups such as Intersex Philippines and Intersex Asia play an increasingly important role in creating community, fostering peer support, and advancing rights claims (CNN Philippines, 2019).

Psychological Self-Image, Identity, and Acceptance

The psychological literature on self-image and identity among intersex individuals draws on several foundational theoretical traditions. Rosenberg's (1965) three-element model of self-image—self-perception, interpretation of others' perceptions,

and ideal self—provides a framework for understanding how intersex individuals construct a sense of self in the face of social stigma and biological ambiguity. Higgins's (1987, 1989) self-discrepancy theory, which posits that psychological distress arises from perceived gaps between actual, ideal, and ought selves, is particularly relevant for intersex individuals, who often experience profound discrepancy between their biological reality, social presentation, and inner sense of identity.

Van de Grift et al. (2018) conducted a European multicenter study examining body image and self-esteem among individuals with DSDs, finding that psychological well-being was significantly associated with the quality of psychosocial support received and the degree to which individuals felt in control of decisions about their own bodies. Roen (2019) similarly emphasizes the importance of autonomy and person-centered care in supporting positive psychosocial outcomes for intersex individuals. Brichacek et al. (2018) further document the role of basic psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—in maintaining positive body image in the face of external pressure.

Regarding sexual orientation and relational identity, Frank (2017) has documented the complex and often anxiety-laden dynamics of dating and intimate relationships for intersex individuals, who must navigate fears of rejection, disclosure, and external judgment in relational contexts. McInroy et al. (2021) and Jacobson and Joel (2020) have further examined the diversity of sexual identities among intersex individuals, noting that intersex status does not determine sexual orientation and that intersex individuals may identify across the full spectrum of sexual and gender identities. The sense of belonging to a community of shared experience—facilitated by intersex peer groups and forums—has been identified as a critical protective factor for mental health and self-acceptance (Over, 2016; Petersen et al., 2019).

Taken together, the literature converges on the conclusion that positive self-image and self-acceptance among intersex individuals are not inevitable outcomes of biological resolution, but rather achievements that require social support, personal autonomy, community belonging, and the capacity to construct meaningful narratives from experiences of difference and adversity.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Intersex individuals are born with sex characteristics that do not conform to medical and social norms for heteronormative bodies (Carpenter, 2016). Throughout history, the journey of self-knowledge has been particularly fraught for intersex individuals (Pikraenou, 2019). The central question guiding this study is: How do intersex individuals accept their self-image?

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the perceived self-image of the respondents?
2. How is self-image embraced by the respondents?
3. What are the factors being faced in accepting self-image?
4. What constitutes a fully accepted self-image?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design to explore the lived experiences of Filipino intersex individuals with regard to their self-image. Phenomenological research is a method in which researchers describe and identify the essence of "lived experience" of human experience about a specific phenomenon as described by informants, allowing for a profound understanding of participants' inner worlds by deriving universal meaning from their statements (Neubauer et

al., 2019). The research locale encompassed the entire Philippines, reflecting the small and geographically dispersed nature of the visible intersex community, estimated at approximately 40 organized members nationwide at the time of data collection (CNN Philippines, 2019). Ten Filipino intersex individuals affiliated with Intersex Philippines were selected through purposive and snowball sampling, meeting criteria of Filipino citizenship, age of legal majority (18 years or older), affiliation with Intersex Philippines, and a minimum of one year since discovery of intersex status. Data were collected through an online focus group discussion conducted via Zoom Conferencing, titled "Round Table: A Focus Group Discussion," which lasted approximately five hours and was video recorded for transcription.

A semi-structured questionnaire—validated by three experts including an intersex advocate and officer-in-charge of Intersex Philippines, a registered psychometrician and clinical psychology master's degree holder, and a Doctor of Philosophy and research expert—served as the interview guide, with additional probing questions generated organically during discussion. Psychological debriefing was conducted following the FGD in two breakout rooms facilitated by psychology and counselling professionals. All data were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using Colaizzi's (1978) seven-step descriptive phenomenological method, which proceeds through familiarization, identification of significant statements, formulation of meanings, clustering of themes, development of exhaustive description, production of the fundamental structure, and verification with participants. Participant anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout, in compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173) and established ethical principles governing research with LGBTQIA+ populations (Henrickson et al., 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study explored how intersex individuals view and accept their self-image. Through focus group discussion, data analysis of participants' responses yielded nine emergent themes that collectively address the study's research problems.

Table 1: Emergent Themes

Code	Theme
A	Appearance and Aesthetics of Intersex Individuals
C	Conceived Inward Being of the Intersex Individuals
1.C	Conceived Biological Being of the Intersex Individuals
1.E	Encountered Mismatching
1.P	Producing the Totality of Self-Image
1.T	The Journey to Acceptance
1.A	Added Help of Intersex Forums
1.N	Narrative of Acceptance in the Point of View of Intersex Individuals
1.CE	Celebrating the Acceptance of Self-Image

As shown in Table 1, the nine emergent themes arose from participants' responses and sufficiently addressed all four research problems. Themes A, C, 1.C, and 1.E collectively answer the first research problem regarding the perceived self-image of intersex respondents. Theme 1.P addresses the second research problem concerning how self-image is embraced. Themes 1.T and 1.A address the third research problem regarding the factors faced in accepting self-image. Finally, Themes 1.N and 1.CE address the fourth research problem concerning what constitutes a fully accepted self-image. The researchers note that a 100% level of agreement was achieved in the clustering of statements (see Appendix III). Where participants chose not to respond to specific questions, the researchers respected their right to silence, recognizing the sensitive nature of the subject matter.

Theme 1: Appearance and Aesthetics of Intersex Individuals

Table 2: Intersex Individuals' Body Image: Appearance and Clothing

Subtheme	Formulated Meaning
Intersex Individual's Physical Appearance	Participants described mismatched physical features that diverged from their assigned sex. Physical characteristics were predominantly masculine despite female documentation, or otherwise did not align with the gender recorded in legal documents.
Clothed for Approval	Participants were required to dress in accordance with their documented sex, regardless of their physical appearance or personal preference. Examples included wearing female attire (e.g., skirts and bras) to comply with institutional or familial expectations.
Struggles in Clothing	Participants reported significant distress in conforming to gendered dress expectations — particularly being required to wear female clothing despite identifying differently.

Subtheme 1.1: Intersex Individual's Physical Appearance

Intersex people possess physical traits that do not conform to the traditional constructs of male or female bodies (Carpenter, 2018). Consistent with the literature, participants in this study reported physical characteristics that visibly diverged from those expected of their assigned sex at birth. Lundberg et al. (2018) further noted that intersex individuals employ diverse vocabulary when discussing their bodies depending on the social and therapeutic context, a pattern similarly observed in participants' accounts. Representative statements include:

"ako po ay I am female. And ang preference ko po ay female and parang sa physical attributes ko po ay parang may pagkamasculine po" (Transcript 1, Participant 3, Lines 125–228)

"bali po kung makikita nyo po ako sa personal ang pangagatawan ko po ay panglalake boses ko po panglalake tinutubnan din po ako ng full berg sa aking muka" (Transcript 1, Participant 9, Lines 350–352)

"yung physical features natin ay kumbaga hindi match sa mga document natin" (Transcript 2, Participant 1, Lines 533–534)

"Walang sign nang pagiging babae. Maliban nalang kung magdadamat ako ng pambabae" (Transcript 3, Participant 6, Lines 1779–1780)

These accounts reflect the contradiction described by Carpenter (2018) and Roen (2019), wherein intersex bodies are simultaneously over-medicalized and socially rendered invisible. The misalignment between physical presentation and assigned documentation is a recurring source of distress, reinforcing the need for non-pathologizing frameworks in understanding intersex bodies.

Subtheme 1.2: Intersex Individual's Clothing

Subtheme 1.2.1: Clothed for Approval

Clothing functions as a site of gender performance and social belonging (Chauhan et al., 2019; Conley, 2017). From birth, gendered clothing communicates societal expectations — blue for boys, pink for girls — and serves as a primary vehicle through which gender norms are enforced (Conley, 2017, p. 134). For intersex participants, clothing became a tool of conformity rather than self-expression, as they were required to dress according to their documented sex regardless of their physical presentation or personal identity. This is illustrated in the following accounts:

"nirequired po ako na panglalaki po ang damit ko" (Transcript 1, Participant 9, Line 1632)

"dun sa policy ng school dahil kailangan mag skirt kabit masakit sa loob mo mag skirt kabit yung pangalan mo pambabae tanag sayo" (Transcript 4, Participant 1, Lines 1708–1711)

"Siyempre naiilang po ako dahil sa school pag susuotin ka ng pallada pero gusto kong suotin ay pang lalaki. Wala naman akong magagawa dahil iyon ang nakasulat sa dokumento" (Transcript 3, Participant 7, Lines 1613–1616)

Subtheme 1.2.2: Struggles in Clothing

Reilly and McGuire (2018) noted that while some individuals use clothing to challenge gender norms, many others employ it to affirm and communicate gendered expectations. For intersex participants, this meant engaging in dressing practices that caused psychological discomfort in order to maintain social approval. As the following statements reveal, the struggle with clothing was deeply tied to the mismatch between participants' bodily realities and their assigned gender documentation:

"need ko pang magsuot ng bra tapos maglagay pa ng foam para lang magmukhang may suso" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 953–954)

"I was raised as female pero since na kid ano nilalaban ko yun. Actually, I don't like wearing girl's clothes" (Transcript 1, Participant 5, Lines 217–219)

Theme 2: Conceived Inward Being of the Intersex Individuals

According to Kant (1997), the inner self comprises psychological states, reasoning, feelings, intuitions, values, beliefs, personality, thoughts, emotions, spirituality, desires, and purposes. This theme examines the inward dimensions of intersex participants' identities, encompassing their sexual preferences, psychological outlooks, and relational experiences.

Subtheme 2.1: Preference

Subtheme 2.1.1: Intersex People's Affection

Sexual orientation among intersex individuals can be complex and does not necessarily correspond to either their assigned sex or their gender identity (McInroy et al., 2021). The gender binary presents particular challenges to flexible sexuality, as sexual scripts and intimacy norms typically assume male or female sexed bodies (Frank, 2017). Participants articulated clear sexual preferences, as seen in the following statements:

"Ako, ever since attracted po ako sa babae banggang sa nalaman kong intersex ako, sa babae parin ako attracted" (Transcript 3, Participant 6, Lines 1591–1594)

"Sa usaping feelings, na-attract po ako talaga sa lalaki. Never akong na-attract sa babae, kumbaga na-insecure lang ako sa ibang mga babae kasi feeling ko iba ako" (Transcript 2, Participant 10, Lines 1636–1640)

Subtheme 2.1.2: Dating Anxiety

Frank (2017) described dating as a dyadic interaction centered on mutually gratifying behaviors that may evolve into emotional commitment and sexual intimacy. For intersex individuals, dating is further complicated by fears of rejection, stigma related to genital or gonadal variation, and the vulnerability inherent in self-disclosure. Participants expressed significant anxiety around relational contexts:

"Sinasabi nila na hindi daw ako makapagrelasyon. Inisip ko na yun na bakit ako papasok sa isang bagay na alam kong ano" (Transcript 2, Participant 10, Lines 1435–1437)

"Nagpaligaw ako, pero feeling ko kapag naging kami, hindi ko rin kaya" (Transcript 3, Participant 7, Lines 1617–1619)

Subtheme 2.2: Psychological Outlook

Despite the challenges associated with being intersex, participants demonstrated notable psychological resilience and a positive orientation toward life. Their responses reflected alignment with the key components of Seligman's (2011) PERMA model — positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishments — particularly in the ways participants derived purpose from their experiences:

"kung anuman yung hamon ng bubay, at hamon ng pagiging isang intersex kung anuman yung kinakabara sa akin po bindi ako gumigive up or wala kong intent na mag-give up" (Transcript 1, Participant 6, Lines 279–283)

"Maging thankful nalang tayo everyday ang birap kasi mabuhay kung puro sakit, puot, galit, birap at diskriminasyon ganyan" (Transcript 5, Participant 3, Lines 2120–2125)

"parang I am unique pero sa mata ng Diyos I am perfect" (Transcript 5, Participant 3, Line 113)

Theme 3: Conceived Biological Being of the Intersex Individuals

Intersex is a congenital condition arising from genetic, chromosomal, or hormonal variation — or a combination thereof (Monro et al., 2017). This theme captures participants' awareness and lived experience of their biological realities, organized under three subthemes: menstruation, infertility, and other biological challenges.

Subtheme 3.1: Menstruation

Whether an intersex individual experiences menstruation depends on the presence and functionality of reproductive organs at birth (Natracare, n.d.). The majority of participants did not experience menstruation, and this biological difference — diverging from normative female experience — was a recurring point of awareness and, at times, social vulnerability:

"Ab pinanganak po akong babae but unfortunately hindi ko po nararanasan yung mga nararanasan ng mga babae, tulad ng monthly period or kaya yung puberty stage" (Transcript 1, Participant 4, Lines 153–157)

"at hindi rin po ako nireregla ganon din po sa aking overall na chemistry" (Transcript 1, Participant 9, Lines 365–366)

Subtheme 3.2: Infertility

Infertility is a common but not universal experience among intersex individuals, and may be compounded by medical interventions undertaken during childhood or adolescence (Jones, 2019). Jones (2017) observed that infertility carries particular social weight for women, who have historically been characterized as having 'not only flawed bodies but also spoilt identities' when unable to conceive. Participants expressed this dimension of their experience with both resignation and longing:

"kasi hindi ka naman mabubuntis ganun" (Transcript 2, Participant 4, Line 883)

"Hindi ko man lang mararanasan magkapamilya, magka anak tapos para at tingin lang sa'yo baldado, retireded kasi ganyan lang yung sitwasyon mo" (Transcript 5, Participant 2, Lines 2069–2071)

Subtheme 3.3: Biological Problems

Intersex individuals may present with variations in chromosomal pairings, genital anatomy, or hormonal regulation that constitute their intersex condition (Rowlands & Amy, 2018). Participants demonstrated awareness of these underlying biological factors, as confirmed by medical consultations:

"ibigsabihin po neto wala po akong uterus wala po akong ovaries" (Transcript 1, Participant 9, Lines 345–346)

"Ang may problema kasi sa amin eh hormones, so sa akin bilang confirmation ng doctor ko, hormone ang may problema sa akin" (Transcript 2, Participant 2, Lines 677–679)

Theme 4: Encountered Mismatching

Moschella (2019) introduced the concept of 'brain sex' to describe the biological phenomenon in which an individual's internal sense of gender diverges from their bodily presentation. This theme examines the various forms of mismatching experienced by participants — across legal documentation, chromosomal data, and emotional experience.

Subtheme 4.1: Legal Documents

Having a legal gender marker that does not correspond to one's

physical appearance or identity can result in discrimination, exclusion, and daily exposure in public and institutional settings (Holzer, 2020). Participants articulated the distress of living with documentation that did not reflect their bodies or identities:

"sa Birth certificate po siguro sa papel oo babae pero yung puso ko po saka damdamin lalaki pano ko naman po I aline yun e magkaiba po yun" (Transcript 4, Participant 6, Lines 1858–1860)

"kasi dahil hindi match doon ako nakaranas ng diskriminasyon at dahil doon sa diskriminasyon na yon doon sumusunod yung depresyon" (Transcript 2, Participant 1, Lines 577–579)

Subtheme 4.2: Karyotype

A karyotype refers to the full complement of an individual's chromosomes and is used diagnostically to confirm intersex conditions (National Human Genome Research Institute, n.d.). Participants reported experiencing a mismatch between their karyotype and their physical presentation, a finding confirmed by endocrinological consultation:

"Kaya nga nung sinabi sa akin ng doctor noon endocrinologist na hindi match yung Karyotype mo" (Transcript 4, Participant 1, Lines 1685–1686)

Subtheme 4.3: Emotions

Research in intersex studies demonstrates that gender feelings, identity, and behavior are not reliably predicted by genital appearance (Carpenter, 2018; Fausto-Sterling, 2019; Meoded Danon, 2018). Participants similarly reported emotional experiences that did not correspond to their physical presentation:

"meron din sa amin parang vice versa di nag ma-match yung pisikal versus dun sa emosyonal yung sa kaloloban" (Transcript 4, Participant 6, Lines 1888–1889)

Theme 5: Producing the Totality of Self-Image

Body image formation is partly evaluative and affective, and is sustained by psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Brichacek et al., 2018). Dalke (2017) advocates for intersex individuals' right to autonomous decision-making regarding their own bodies. Participants expressed this autonomy clearly as the central mechanism through which they constructed and affirmed their self-image:

"kasi dapat masunod yung may katawan no. Kasi kami yung magdadala, kami yung kasi sobra sobra na yung pinagdaanan namin. Kaya its time naman na kami yung masunod sa gusto namin" (Transcript 4, Participant 1, Lines 1695–1698)

"E! Bakit di ko nalang sundin ang kagustuhan ko saka pangalawa yung itsura ko naman po talaga di mo naman ma ano na babae, baka lalo lang po ako mahirapan kako" (Transcript 4, Participant 6, Lines 1845–1849)

"depende sa kin kung paano ko I pe-perceive kung ang sarili ko pano ko sya tanggapin" (Transcript 1, Participant 10, Lines 382–384)

The findings reveal that the formation of a coherent self-image among intersex individuals is not a passive process, but an active, autonomous one — driven by internal self-assessment and the alignment of one's felt identity with chosen self-presentation. This is consistent with PERMA's emphasis on autonomy and self-determination (Seligman, 2011) as foundational to psychological well-being.

Theme 6: The Journey to Acceptance

Drawing on Kübler-Ross's (1969) seminal model of grief — comprising denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance — this theme traces the emotional trajectory of intersex individuals toward self-acceptance. As adapted by Bregman (2017), this model has been applied across diverse life-

altering phenomena. Participants confirmed that they traversed these emotional stages, though not necessarily in a linear sequence:

"lahat naman siguro kami dumaan sa ganyan, kaya lang di talaga namin nilanod" (Transcript 4, Participant 3, Lines 1790–1791)

Subtheme 6.1: Denial

Denial functions as an initial coping mechanism following the shock of diagnosis, enabling individuals to process an overwhelming reality at a manageable pace (Kübler-Ross, 1969). Participants reported questioning the validity of their intersex status even after medical confirmation:

"noong nalaman ko po na intersex po ako, ano ba yung reaksiyon ko noon. Teke po, iisipin ko lang. Una kasi sabi ko sa sarili ko, intersex ba ko, gumaganon pa ko eh" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1253–1259)

"kabiti na po nag-undergo na ko ng medical, kabiti na nalaman ko na parang hindi pa din ako convince na tanggap ko talaga" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1088–1089)

Subtheme 6.2: Anger

Anger in grief often manifests as an outward projection of responsibility or an existential questioning of fairness (Gregory, n.d.). Mental health professionals consider it a critical and necessary stage through which grief must be genuinely experienced to be resolved. Participants expressed anger in ways that reflected both outward attribution and self-directed frustration:

"ako po tinapon ko lahat po ng pictures ko e nung panabong ako ay Jennifer pa no, pero minsan nga na realize ko na mali pala ako" (Transcript 2, Participant 1, Lines 1253–1259)

"So minsan ako nagsasabi ako kila kuya jeff na sa dami ng tao bakit ako pa talaga pero minsan irereverse ko naman na hindi" (Transcript 5, Participant 2, Lines 2076–2078)

Subtheme 6.3: Depression

Depression in the grief model reflects a confrontation with reality — a withdrawal from life following the recognition of an irreversible change (Gregory, n.d.). Participants described profound feelings of helplessness and resignation, occasionally accompanied by passive suicidal ideation:

"Iyon po yung tumatak sa akin na feeling, kasi oo alam mo na intersex ka kasi parang tanggap mo na kasi wala ka namang magagawa" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1076–1079)

"na tanggap ko na wala ng magbabago kabiti ano pang gawin ko kabiti pa magbigti pa ko dyan o anumang mga depresyon wala ng magbabago" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1102–1104)

"dumadating sa point na bakit di mo pweding gawin yung gusto mo kaya umiyak ka nalang sa taas kasi walang nakakaintindi sayo walang nakakaalam ng pinagdadaanan mo no" (Transcript 4, Participant 7, Lines 1912–1914)

Theme 7: Added Help of Intersex Forums

Research on human belonging underscores the role of group membership in cognitive development, social coping, and identity formation (Over, 2016). Levine and Moreland's (1994) model of group socialization further posits that individuals and their groups co-evolve through sustained interaction — a dynamic that was clearly evident in how participants described the role of Intersex Philippines forums in facilitating their acceptance.

Subtheme 7.1: The Impact of the Forum

Petersen et al. (2019) demonstrated that social connection is emotionally activated when situations are relevant to an individual's values, beliefs, and relational attachments. For intersex participants, the experience of meeting others who

shared their condition created a powerful sense of validation and belonging:

"syempre iba pa din pag nakakausap ka or mayroon kang nakabara na katulad mo. Yung parang mafeel mo na parang parebas kayo ng pinagdadaanan" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1035–1038)

"Basta the time na yari yung forum namin oh okay na tanggap ko naman na yun lahat" (Transcript 4, Participant 2, Lines 1777–1778)

"kung ano yung mga negative impact as in lahat after forum. Doon talaga kami nagkaroon ng lakas ng loob na yes tanggapin natin kung sino or ano tayo. Kasi at the end of the day ikaw at ikaw lang yung makakatulong sa sarili mo" (Transcript 2, Participant 7, Lines 1303–1307)

These findings affirm that peer-based support structures are not merely supplementary but constitute a meaningful catalyst in the intersex acceptance process. The forum provided a structured space for identity affirmation, collective meaning-making, and the development of the courage necessary for full self-acceptance.

Theme 8: Narrative of Acceptance in the Point of View of Intersex Individuals

Park and Folkman's (1997) meaning-making model distinguishes between global meanings — broad orienting beliefs — and situational meanings, which are appraised in specific contexts. Participants offered rich, subjective definitions of acceptance that reflected both dimensions. Rather than a single moment of resolution, acceptance was consistently described as an evolving and deeply personal process:

"Tingnan ko po kasi ang acceptance is a process. Bawat isa sa atin iba-iba ng pagtanggap" (Transcript 2, Participant 1, Lines 621–622)

"Para sa akin po, iyon po iyong pinakabest na nangyari sa akin bilang intersex person, hindi lang bilang dahil sa natanggap ko yung sarili ko" (Transcript 2, Participant 6, Lines 1059–1062)

"hindi natin kailangan madaliin ang proseso, kung baga ang desisyon ng pagtanggap ay sa sarili hindi natin makukuha sa ibang tao" (Transcript 5, Participant 1, Lines 2038–2042)

These accounts underscore the non-linear and individualized nature of acceptance — a finding consistent with the Kübler-Ross model's caveat that stages of grief are neither sequential nor universal (Stroebe et al., 2017). The intersex individuals in this study demonstrated that acceptance is ultimately an intrinsic decision, arrived at in one's own time and on one's own terms.

Theme 9: Celebrating the Acceptance of Self-Image

Self-acceptance, as defined by Pillay (2016), involves acknowledging one's attributes — positive and negative — while cultivating self-protection from external criticism and believing in one's own capabilities. Ryff and Keyes (1995) similarly identified self-acceptance as a cornerstone of psychological well-being, emphasizing the importance of a positive attitude toward all aspects of oneself. For intersex participants, reaching this stage represented not simply a cessation of struggle, but an active and celebratory embrace of their identity:

Subtheme 9.1: Self-Acceptance

"kasi sino bang tatanggap sa sarili mo kundi sarili mo lang din" (Transcript 4, Participant 2, Line 1762)

"yung acceptance pag talagang tanggap na tanggap mo na lahat yun kabiti gaano kabirap tatamanan mo na lang. Ganun yung pinagdadaan ko" (Transcript 2, Participant 3, Lines 638–640)

"parang siguro self-acceptance nalang rin po talaga and siguro nabago yung motivation ko sa bubay ko na parang ano e YOLO you only live once and kumbaga live your life to the fullest iisa lang kasi yung bubay natin so make it colorful make it meaningful" (Transcript 4, Participant 7, Lines 1892–1897)

"be yourself nalang be yourself, be your own kind of human individual as intersex diba yun lang po" (Transcript 4, Participant 7, Lines 1905–1907)

"embrace ko na lang yung pagiging gamito so naovercome ko na" (Transcript 2, Participant 8, Lines 1324–1325)

"Kung tanggap mo na ang iyong sarili wag mong isipin yung sasabihin ng iba isipin mo kung sino at ano ka talaga wag mong pakikngan ang sasabihin ng iba kasi ikaw yan hindi sila yung nasa situasyon mo" (Transcript 5, Participant 7, Lines 2290–2295)

The above accounts reflect a transformation in orientation — from concealment and shame to authenticity and humor in the face of adversity. Participants' narratives demonstrate that a fully accepted self-image is not merely tolerant of one's intersex identity but is actively celebratory of it. This finding aligns with the PERMA model's components of meaning and accomplishment (Seligman, 2011), as participants articulated a sense of purpose derived from their unique existence and the resilience they cultivated through it.

SYNTHESIS OF FINDINGS

Taken together, the nine themes constitute a coherent phenomenological narrative of how intersex individuals in the Philippine context perceive, negotiate, and ultimately accept their self-image. The perceived self-image of intersex respondents (Research Problem 1) is characterized by profound incongruence — between physical appearance and legal documentation, between biological reality and social expectation, and between inner emotional experience and external presentation (Themes 1–4). This mismatching is not merely physical but permeates the intersex individual's psychological and relational worlds.

Self-image is embraced through autonomy (Research Problem 2) — a deliberate, internally-driven act of choosing who one is, independent of medical prescription or social norm (Theme 5). The factors that must be navigated in this process (Research Problem 3) include the emotional stages of denial, anger, and depression — mirroring Kübler-Ross's (1969) model — as well as the structural invisibility of intersex individuals in Philippine institutional and legal frameworks (Themes 6–7). Critically, peer support through intersex forums plays a decisive facilitative role, providing the communal validation that makes the solitary work of acceptance more possible.

Finally, a fully accepted self-image (Research Problem 4) is understood by intersex participants not as the resolution of all struggle, but as an ongoing commitment to authenticity — characterized by self-directedness, embrace of one's totality, and the capacity to find meaning, humor, and purpose in one's unique existence (Themes 8–9). The PERMA model (Seligman, 2011) and the Kübler-Ross framework (1969) together illuminate how intersex individuals move from grief and concealment toward flourishing — a process that is deeply individualized, non-linear, and ultimately self-determined.

CONCLUSION

This phenomenological study documents the complex, multi-layered journey through which Filipino intersex individuals come to perceive, form, and ultimately accept their self-image. The findings reveal that intersex individuals navigate profound biological, social, and psychological mismatches—between their bodies and legal documents, between social expectations and inner identity, and between cultural norms and personal truth—before arriving at an integrated and accepted sense of self.

In response to the first research question, the perceived self-image of intersex individuals is characterized by a fundamental incongruence across multiple dimensions: physical appearance, biological functioning, legal documentation, and emotional

identity. Participants experienced their bodies as sites of contradiction, in which masculine and feminine attributes coexisted in ways that defied binary categorization and generated persistent social friction.

In response to the second research question, self-image is embraced through the exercise of personal autonomy—the deliberate decision to follow one's own desires, sexual satisfaction, and self-perception rather than the prescriptions of medical authorities, institutional policies, or social norms. Autonomy emerges as the cornerstone of positive self-image formation.

In response to the third research question, the factors faced in accepting self-image include denial, anger, and depression—stages consistent with Kübler-Ross's (1969) grief model—as well as the transformative support provided by peer community through intersex forums. The experience of belonging to a community of shared experience accelerates and deepens the acceptance process.

In response to the fourth research question, a fully accepted self-image is characterized by being one's authentic self, embracing one's intersex identity, finding purpose and meaning in one's unique existence, and maintaining optimism in the face of ongoing adversity. Acceptance is understood as an active, ongoing achievement rather than a passive state.

This study fulfills an important gap in the scientific literature by centering the humanness and subjective experience of intersex individuals in the Philippines. It provides an empirical foundation for clinical, educational, and policy interventions that respect intersex individuals' autonomy, support their psychological well-being, and advocate for their full inclusion in Philippine society. Future research should expand the sample, employ mixed-methods designs, and explore additional dimensions of intersex lived experience including intimate relationships, parenting aspirations, and the specific impacts of pending legislation such as the SOGIE Equality Bill.

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